

MONTESSORI METHOD

Valijonova Sugdiyona, Najmiddinova Sarvara

Fergana regional branch of Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture

Abstract: This article describes how to increase the self-confidence of children three to twelve years old by using the Montessori method, the role of supportive teachers, and a new way of teaching preschoolers.

Keywords: maria, method, preschooler, method, materials, process.

(Montessori) Maria was born on August 31, 1870 in Chiaravalle (Italy). She is a teacher, psychologist, doctor, the first woman to receive a doctorate. Maria Montessori was twice awarded the “Nobel Peace” prize. As for her methodology, after graduating from the university of Rome, she worked with mentally retarded and disabled children and tested her method on these children. The success of the Montessori method is that these children like other healthy children, have achieved the same results in learning and life. The Montessori method is widely used throughout the world (more than hundred countries).

Montessori Method:

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Another unique aspect of the Montessori method is that it emphasizes a learning environment tailored to each child's specific ability and needs. If you were to sit down with a Montessori teacher, you'd find that they could spend hours talking to you about the curriculum, their personal philosophies and the wonderful experiences they've had with so many children. Montessori has made a huge difference in the lives of many children simply because it is designed to embrace a child's unique individuality and celebrate their personal abilities. Multi-age groupings of children are a unique classroom component of the Montessori program. The reason for multi-age groupings within the classroom is twofold: Younger students naturally learn more from their older peers, and older students tend to retain more information when they teach it to younger ones. Besides that, having children of different ages and stages together in the classroom mimics the real world, teaching students how to get along with people of different ages and interests. Teaching in this manner can often turn the joy of learning into a chore for children, taking away the fun of discovery.

In the Montessori environment, the teacher's role is to encourage children's natural ability to discover and create. The Montessori approach recognizes children learn best when teachers encourage them to use their natural creativity and intelligence to gather information and make discoveries. Their reward is the feeling of pride they get when they master a new concept.

Rather than standing in front of the class sharing facts, a Montessori teacher plans activities designed to introduce and reinforce concepts. These are chosen based on the ages and abilities of the students

in the class and often take a hands-on approach to learning. Once the child chooses their activity, the teacher then assumes the role of a guide, answering questions or subtly leading the student into discovery. Accreditation means a school has accountability and has been recognized for its authentic practice of Montessori principles. Many schools take bits and pieces of the Montessori curriculum, but when a school is accredited, it means they follow the complete curriculum without variation. In other words, it means you're guaranteed to get the full Montessori curriculum.

Ultimately, accreditation is there to give you peace of mind. It tells you that your child's school is subject to regular review of its practices and has been recognized and certified by an independent organization for its adherence to Montessori principles and best practices. MYTH: Montessori Schools Are Faith-Based Programs

FACT: Montessori is not a faith-based program, nor is it based in new-age philosophies. In fact, the Montessori curriculum is more than 100 years old and was created by a doctor whose experiences working in both medicine and education shaped her theories about how children learn and grow.

MYTH: All Montessori Schools Are the Same

FACT: Although accredited Montessori schools follow certain principles and guidelines, depending on how a certain school applies the principles Dr. Montessori established, you're sure to find some variation among each Montessori school. That's why it's important to make sure you understand what a true Montessori curriculum looks like and the foundations behind its methods. Knowing the basics will prepare you for selecting the best environment for your child, regardless of their age.

MYTH: Young Children Won't Grasp Montessori Principles

FACT: Parents often ask us, "What's the best time to start my child in a Montessori program?" While there is no age limit, we find somewhere between 18 and 36 months is the ideal time to introduce Montessori principles to a child. In the early years of Montessori education, children spend much time on sensory activities, designed to develop their senses of seeing, hearing, smelling, touch and taste. That is what drives the program at Sapiientia Montessori School.

As they move into their elementary school years, Montessori students will move into more abstract topics, applying what they are learning to real-world situations. This effort to help them organize their thoughts will benefit them as they continue to grow. In the adolescent years, the Montessori program relies on this foundation to prepare students to combine reason and emotion to understand the broader concepts of equity, justice and freedom.

MYTH: Montessori Teachers Don't Have the Same Levels of Education and Training Traditional Teachers Do.

FACT: Montessori teachers are some of the best and brightest educators out there. They come to us with an impressive combination of experience and advanced degrees that back up their outstanding abilities to lead a classroom. What makes Montessori teachers special is that they are able to focus first and foremost of cultivating an atmosphere of creativity and discovery that will encourage learning and growth in children of all ages and abilities. Their patience and creativity are unparalleled, and their love of learning knows no bounds.

Conclusion.

In my opinion, children learn to live in society in which they live, the culture of behavior, friendly communication. Montessori Method which is one of the most effective, includes children's natural interests rather than formal teaching.

References:

1. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>.
2. Association Montessori Internationale (AMI)
3. <https://montessori-ami.org>
4. "A Guide to the Montessori Method" Gerald Lee Gutek.